

ENA Metagenome Data Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a metagenome dataset to the test version of the **ENA Webin-CLI submission** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a teal header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is titled 'Account Details' and contains several input fields for registration information:

- Abbreviated center name
- Full center name
- Laboratory Name
- Address
- Country
- Password
- Confirm Password

Below the 'Account Details' section, there is a 'Contact Information' section with a link to 'Add At Least One Contact' and a plus sign icon. At the bottom, there is a 'No Sensitive Data' section with a checkbox and the text: 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the

test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

Content of this Practical

ENA Metagenome Data Submission Practical	1
Content of this Practical	3
The Scenario	4
The Study	4
The Sample	6
The Read Data	9
Submit Read Read Data using Webin-CLI	9
Primary Metagenome Assembly	12
Binned Metagenome Assembly	15
Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)	18

The Scenario

You have sequenced a **metagenome sample derived from the Mediterranean Sea** for a study attempting to identify marine microbiome. Metagenome sequencing to obtain raw reads was done on an **Illumina HiSeq 2000**. **Primary metagenomes** were assembled using MEGAHIT v.1.2.7. **Binning** was performed in MetaBAT v.2.12.1. Bin completeness, contamination and strain heterogeneity were estimated. Bins scoring $\geq 50\%$ completeness, $< 10\%$ contamination and $< 10\%$ strain heterogeneity were retained as MAGs. **MAGs** were de-replicated. In cases where more than one MAG belonged to the same species, the highest-quality MAG was selected as the representative. You will be submitting a set of paired read data files obtained as a result of sequencing and the metagenome assemblies to the **ENA test submission service**. This is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for < 24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

Since you will be using Webin-CLI to only submit your data files, the study and sample registration will be done interactively.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Log in to the Webin test submission service with your account ID and the password:
<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>
2. After logging in, find the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Register study (project)**' button to see the study registration interface:

The screenshot shows the 'Register study (project)' web interface. At the top, there is a header with a hamburger menu icon and the text 'Register study (project)'. Below this is a section titled 'Submission Details' containing several input fields: 'Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *' with a calendar icon, 'Short descriptive study title *', 'Study Name', and 'Detailed study abstract *'. There is also a checkbox labeled 'Will you provide functional genome annotation ?'. At the bottom of the form, there is a section for 'PubMed Citations Registration' with a button labeled 'Add PubMed Citations' and a plus sign icon.

3. Set a **release date** for your study (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
4. The '**Study Name**' field should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.

5. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:

Metagenomic Study of Mediterranean Sea from <Your Town/Lab>

6. When you have completed all required fields, click '**Submit**' and then confirm.
7. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Studies Report**' button to see the study you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.

Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and PRJEB#####

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

The Sample

The next step is to register the sample, which will give other users essential context for the sequence data you are submitting. The sample describes the source biological material of your sequencing work.

In ENA, samples are required to conform to a checklist of values. Checklists define a set of mandatory and recommended values for a given type of sample. It is recommended that you look at these early and make sure you collect all required metadata items for the type of sample you will be registering.

The selection of available checklists can be browsed at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

1. Return to the main page of the Webin Portal and find the 'Samples' tab.

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>

2. Click on the '**Register samples**' button.
3. Expand the section '**Download spreadsheet to register samples**'. You must choose an appropriate checklist of values to be provided for your sample. Browse the range of checklists available.

Note: Please make sure you use a MlxS checklist (Environmental checklist) for metagenomic data.

4. Which samples checklist do you feel is most relevant for the sample you have sequenced?
5. Submitters now have the option of including additional fields in their checklist. It is not necessary to include any additional fields but you can take this opportunity to see which fields are included as mandatory, recommended and optional, what requirements they have, and what else is available.

Click '**Next**' when you're ready.

6. Download the TSV template and open the file in Excel on your computer.

Please note that you should submit your spreadsheet in the same format that you have downloaded it (TSV).

7. When you open the TSV template, the 3rd row will state "#units". Please keep this row intact and enter your data from the 4th row as shown below. This is important for the system to successfully parse your tsv file:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Checklist										
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	project name	collection date	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude)	broad-scale environmental context	local environmental conte
3	#units							DD	DD		
4	xxxxx	soil metagenome	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx
5											
6											
7											
8											
9											

8. Find the appropriate taxon for your sample: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible. In this case for example, “**marine metagenome**” instead of just “**metagenome**”.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search for “metagenome”. You can search for the relevant taxonomy by replacing “metagenome” in the url below:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/metagenome>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

9. Give a 'Unique name' to your sample (sample_alias)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

10. Give your sample a title, this could look something like:

Marine metagenome sample from <Your Town/Lab/Location>.

11. Write a brief description for your sample

12. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going back to the checklist fields page on the Webin Portal and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

13. By the time you have completed this, your sample will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later. Click on ‘**Upload filled spreadsheet to register samples**’ on the Register Samples page and upload/submit the spreadsheet.

14. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Samples' tab to see the sample you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.
Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later:

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and sample metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the raw read data you have obtained. Please download these files from [this folder](#) onto a folder on your computer.

- readfile_R1.fastq.gz
- readfile_R2.fastq.gz

These are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your sample.

Submit Read Read Data using Webin-CLI

The final step is to register the read data produced by sequencing. This will be done using the Webin-CLI program.

NOTE: You will require [Java version 17 or newer](#) for this exercise. If you do not have it on your computer, please install it.

Please have the [latest Webin-CLI version](#) installed.

15. Enter the following command on the terminal:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -help
```

This will output the list of options which can be used with this program. Explore these options to see how the program runs.

16. Now that you have had a look at the program, you'll be submitting reads. let's look at the FASTQ files you'll be submitting in this scenario:

- readfile_R1.fastq.gz
- readfile_R2.fastq.gz

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

17. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file performs three functions:

- Indicates the names of files to submit
- Describes experimental metadata
- States the study and sample the data belong to

The ENA now accepts manifest files in TXT format and JSON format. TXT format is less likely to encounter format errors but if you are confident with JSON file format and would like to give it a try, please go for it. Below is an example of a text manifest file:

'reads_manifest.txt'

```
STUDY TO DO
SAMPLE TO DO
NAME TO DO
INSTRUMENT Illumina HiSeq 2000
INSERT_SIZE 200
LIBRARY_SOURCE METAGENOMIC
LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR
LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON
FASTQ TO DO.fastq.gz
FASTQ TO DO.fastq.gz
```

18. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please download the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY: enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE: enter an accession for the sample you registered earlier (ERSxxx)
- NAME: give the experiment a unique name
- LIBRARY_SOURCE: METAGENOMIC: [Check permitted values for library source](#)
- INSTRUMENT: Illumina HiSeq 2000: [Check permitted values for instrument model](#)
- INSERT_SIZE 200
- LIBRARY_SELECTION PCR: [Check permitted values for library selection](#)
- LIBRARY_STRATEGY AMPLICON: [Check permitted values for library strategy](#)
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the first sequence file
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the second sequence file

19. Now you have everything you need to submit your sequence data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context reads -manifest
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX
-test -validate
```

Note: The -validate command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

20. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context reads -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

21. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided accessions for your experiment and run objects. Note these down and your submission is complete.

Return to the interactive Webin interface and view the sample and run tabs to see the objects you submitted today: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

Primary Metagenome Assembly

Now that you have submitted your reads, you will proceed to submit your primary metagenome assembly which will be linked to the same environmental sample as the reads above. You will be submitting an unannotated primary metagenome in FASTA format.

1. This is an example of how your fasta file would look:

- **'primary_metagenome.fasta.gz'**

```
>primary_metagenome_mediterraneansea_v9_12
TGATAGTTAGTCATATGAAAGCATCATTAGTAAACCACATTGCTTATTATATTGAACAGT
TACATCTGGCTTATTATACAAAGAGAAAACCATACTATTCATACTATTCTCTTTTTGATC
TTCTCAATCTTCTGTTGTTAGATATTCTATTCCCTTGCTCACCATATATACTACTTATGTC
AATATAAGTAGCTCACACCACACTACTACTTCAACTACTACTACTACTGCTACTGCTACT
GTTGTGAACAGAACACGACTGTTGGACAATCGAATCTAATTAAGCAAACATTACAACTA
TCTCAGTAAATTGTAATAACCATACAATGGACAGTTAATTTGCAAATTATCAACCAATAG
TCTCCATGTTCACTGTTTGTCTTTAATTCCATTGCTTAAAGTTACTTGGTAAAATGCAA
.
.
.
>primary_metagenome_mediterraneansea_v9_15
CAACTACTACTACTACTGCTACTGCTACTGTTGTGAACAGAACACGACTGTTGGACAATC
GAATCTAATTAAGCAAACATTACAACTATCTCAGTAAATTGTAATAACCATACAATGGA
CAGTTAATTTGCAAATTATCAACCAATAGTCTCCATGTTCACTGTTTGTCTTTAATTCC
ATTGCTTAAAGTTACTTGGTAAAATGCAAAAACCATACTATGATACTCTATTTGCAAAAT
GTTCTTCAATTGTCTCAGGCTTCATTGTTCCCTGGATTCCACACAAATTGCTTTTTATTT
CTGTTCTTCTCTTCTTGATCTTCTCAATCTTCTGCTGTCAGATACTCTATTCCTTGCTCA
CCATATATACTACTTATGTCAATATAAGTAGCTCACACCACACAACAACAACAACAACA
CAACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTACTATTGCAATTACAAATATAA
```

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

2. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file performs three functions:

- Indicates the names of files to submit
- Describes assembly metadata
- States the study and sample the data belong to

For this exercise, you will be submitting your fasta file with a plain text manifest file. Please prepare your manifest file in a similar format to that shown below:

'primary_manifest.txt'

```
STUDY    TO DO
SAMPLE   TO DO
RUN_REF  TO DOASSEMBLYNAME  TO DO
ASSEMBLY_TYPE  primary metagenome
COVERAGE  200
PROGRAM   MEGAHIT v1.2.7
PLATFORM  ILLUMINA
MOLECULETYPE  genomic DNA
FASTA     primary_metagenome.fasta.gz
```

3. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please download the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY:	enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE:	enter an accession for the sample you registered earlier (ERSxxx)
- RUN_REF	enter an accession for the run you registered earlier (ERRxxx)
- ASSEMBLYNAME	Give the assembly a unique name
- ASSEMBLY_TYPE	primary metagenome
- COVERAGE	200
- PROGRAM	MEGAHIT v1.2.7
- PLATFORM	ILLUMINA
- MOLECULETYPE	genomic DNA
- FASTA	primary_metagenome.fasta.gz

4. Now you have everything you need to submit your primary metagenome data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX
-test -validate
```

Note: The -validate command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

5. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

6. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided an accession for your primary metagenome assembly. Note this down and your submission is complete.

Binned Metagenome Assembly

A **binned metagenome** assembly submission encompasses anything from a set of contigs to a complete genome assembly from a metagenomic source that has been identified as a single-taxon set. There is no limit to the number of bins that can be submitted as part of a metagenomic study as it is recognised that the number of bins produced can be very large.

As part of this exercise, you will be submitting 1 binned assembly. Remember from the presentation that each binned metagenome assembly submission must be associated with a binned sample. This is because a bin is not an assembly of all the data from the collected sample so linking to the environmental sample is misleading and causes incorrect taxonomy assignment. These binned samples represent the taxon sets derived from the environmental sample and hold all metadata related to the taxonomy of that subset as well as methods used to derive it.

For this binned metagenome, your binned sample is composed of “**uncultured Endozoicomonas sp.**”:

[https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/uncultured Endozoicomonas sp.](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/uncultured-Endozoicomonas-sp)

Binned samples should be as specific in taxonomy as they can be and use the specific [ENA binned metagenome checklist](#).

1. In this exercise you will be submitting a fasta file for your binned metagenome assembly along with its binned sample in the manifest file.
 - binned_metagenome.fasta.gz
 - binned_manifest.json

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

2. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file usually performs three functions. In this case, you will be submitting your binned assembly together with your binned sample with webin-CLI using a JSON file, so your manifest file performs four functions:
 - Indicates the names of files to submit
 - Describes assembly metadata
 - States the study the data belong to
 - Registers the relevant binned sample derived from the environmental sample

You will be submitting your fasta file with a JSON manifest file. Please prepare your manifest file similar to that shown below:

```
'binned_manifest.json'
```

```

{
  "study": "TO DO",
  "sample":
  {
    "alias": "TO DO",
    "title": "TO DO",
    "organism": {
      "taxonId": "TO DO"
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "project name",
        "value": "Binned metagenome from study analysing marine metagenome from the Mediterranean Sea"
      },
      {
        "tag": "assembly software",
        "value": "megahit_v1.2.9"
      },
      {
        ""
      },
      {
        "tag": "ena-checklist",
        "value": "ERC000050"
      }
    ]
  },
  "assemblyname": "TO DO",
  "platform": "Illumina HiSeq 2000",
  "run_ref": "TO DO",
  "assembly_type": "binned metagenome",
  "program": "MetaBAT v.2.12.1",
  "coverage": "50",
  "platform": "ILLUMINA",
  "moleculetype": "genomic DNA",
  "fasta": {
    "value": "binned_metagenome.fasta.gz"
  }
}

```

3. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please download the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY:	enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE:	register as part of exercise - complete missing information in sample
- RUN_REF	enter an accession for the run you registered earlier (ERRxxx)
- ASSEMBLYNAME	Give the assembly a unique name
- ASSEMBLY_TYPE	binned metagenome
- COVERAGE	50
- PROGRAM	MetaBAT v.2.12.1
- PLATFORM	ILLUMINA
- MOLECULETYPE	genomic DNA
- FASTA	binned_metagenome.fasta.gz

4. Now you have everything you need to submit your binned metagenome data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest  
(manifest file name).json -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -validate
```

Note: The `-validate` command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

5. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest  
(manifest file name).json -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

6. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided an accession for your binned metagenome assembly. Note these down and your submission is complete.

Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)

The final exercise in this workshop is to submit your MAG. This is a single-taxon assembly based on one or more binned metagenomes that has been asserted to be a close representation to an actual individual genome.

MAG submissions are submitted at the same level as isolate genomes and are distributed within INSDC in the same way.

There should only be one MAG submitted for each species within a biome. This can be determined using a de-replication step or by choosing the highest quality representative genome for each predicted species.

You have chosen the highest quality de-replicated binned genome to submit as a MAG so as part of this exercise, you will be submitting 1 MAG. Remember from the presentation that each MAG assembly submission must be associated with a MAG sample. This is because a MAG is not an assembly of all the data from the collected sample so linking to the environmental sample is misleading and causes incorrect taxonomy assignment. These MAG samples represent the individual organisms derived from the environmental sample and hold all metadata related to the taxonomy of that subset as well as methods used to derive it.

For this MAG metagenome, your sample is composed of “**uncultured Endozoicomonas sp.**”:

[https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/uncultured Endozoicomonas sp.](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/uncultured%20Endozoicomonas%20sp)

MAG samples should be as specific in taxonomy as they can be and use the specific [GSC MIMAG checklist](#).

1. There should be a fasta file for the unannotated contig level MAG assembly that you will have obtained.

- ‘**MAG.fasta.gz**’

```
>0000973|0000973.1 Endozoicomonas isolate MAG genome assembly
GTCCCCGACCGCCCGCGCAAGGCCGGCGCCGTCCTCGTCCGGCGGCGCGCCGCCCCGCC
CGTCCCGGGCGGGCGCCCGGGGCCCGCGGGACCGGCCGGAGTCGCCATGAAGATCGGCGG
GGACGATGTCGGGGGCGGTTTCGCCCCGTCGGCGGGCCTCGAGCACGGCGCGGTAGGCCGGGC
AGGTCGGGCGCAGGACGTCGTGGGGGCCGACGACGTCGATCCGTCCGGCCCCGGAGCAGGG
CGACGCCGTCGCAGGCGCCCATGACCGCGACGCGGTGGGTGATGACAATGGTCTGTGCAC
CCCTCCTGGCGCTCAGGAGGGCGTCGAGGAACTCCGCCTCGGTGCGGGTGTCCAGCCCCG
CGGTGGGCTCGTCGAGCACGAGGACGTCGGGGTTCGCGCAGCAAACCGCGCGGAGCCCCGA
GGCGCTGCCTCTCGCCGCCGACACGCCGCCCGCGCTCCGCGAGCAGCTCCCCAGGC
CTCCGGGCAGGGCGCGCACGCGGTTCGGCGAGGCGGGCCCCGTTTCGAGGGCCGCCACATCT
CGTCTCCCCGGCGTCGGGGGTTCAGCAGATTGTTCGCGGACGGTGGCCCTGAACACGTGCG
.
.
.
>0000974|0000974.1 Endozoicomonas isolate MAG genome assembly
GGGCCGTCCGCCCCGACGCCGGCGAGGGCGAGGGCTGCACGGGCGCCGGCTGCGCGGGC
GAGAGCGGGGACTGGGCGGGGGCGGGCGAGGACTGGGCGGGCGCGGGCTCCAGCCTCTCC
ACCGGCGCGCCACGAGCGTCGCGTCGGAGGCCGCATCGCCGCCAGGCTCAGCCCAGCG
CCCTCCGCGCTGCGGTGGATGGTGACCATGATGTCGTCGAAGGCGACGTCGAGCGGGGCC
TGGGGCTTGTGGACGCAGACCTCGACCTCCTGGACCCGCCCGTAGGCGAGAACC GCGTCG
GAGACCCGTTTCGGCGAGGGTCTCCAGAAGGTTGACGGGGTTCGCCCTCGATCACGGCGATG
ACGGAGGCGGCCACCTTCCCGTAGTCGATGGCGTCGTTTCAGCGAGTCCGTGACGGCGGGC
ACGGCGGTGCCGCGCCGCCCCAGGCCGAGAGTCACGTCGACGACGAAGAGCTGACCCTCC
CGGCGTTTCGGATGGCAGGACGCCGTGGCGGCCACGGGCCGACAACCCGGTTCAGCCGGATC
GTGTCAACGTCGGGTGCGGGGGTGTCTATCGTGTTTTCCTTCCACAGTGAGGCGGTTTCGGA
CGGCGTCCCGGCTGGCCGGGACCTCATGAACTCGCACGGCCAGGCGCCTGCGGCGGGCGG
CGAGGGCCGTGGTGGCGGGCGGTGGCGGCGTCGCGGGCCAGCGGGTTCGGCGGGCGACGTCGT
CGGGCAGGGCGAGGGCGAGGAAGCGCTTTCGGGAGGCCCCGATGAGGACGGGGCGGGCGCA
GGTCTTCGCGCAGGCGGGCGGTGGCGGCCAGCAGCCGCCAGGACTGCTCGTGGGTCTTGG
CGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGGCGGG
```

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

2. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file usually performs three functions. In this case, you will be submitting your MAG assembly together with your MAG sample with webin-CLI using a JSON file, so your manifest file performs four functions:
 - Indicates the names of files to submit
 - Describes assembly metadata
 - States the study the data belong to
 - Registers the relevant MAG sample derived from the environmental sample

You will be submitting your fasta file with a JSON manifest file. Please prepare your manifest file in the following format:

'MAG_manifest.json'

```

{
  "study": "TO DO",
  "sample":
  {
    "alias": "TO DO",
    "title": "TO DO",
    "organism": {
      "taxonId": "TO DO"
    },
    "attributes": [
      {
        "tag": "project name",
        "value": "MAG from study analysing marine metagenome from the Mediterranean Sea"
      },
      {
        "tag": "assembly quality",
        "value": "Single contiguous sequence without gaps or ambiguities with a consensus"
      },
      {
        "tag": "binning software",
        "value": "MetaBAT v.2.12.1"
      },
      {
        ""
      },
      {
        ""
      },
      {
        ""
      }
    ],
    "assemblyname": "TO DO",
    "platform": "Illumina HiSeq 2000",
    "run_ref": "TO DO",
    "assembly_type": "Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)",
    "program": "MetaBAT v.2.12.1",
    "coverage": "50",
    "platform": "ILLUMINA",
    "moleculetype": "genomic DNA",
    "fasta": {
      "value": "MAG.fasta.gz"
    }
  }
}

```

3. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please download the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY:	enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE:	register as part of exercise - complete missing information in sample
- RUN_REF	enter an accession for the run you registered earlier (ERRxxx)
- ASSEMBLYNAME	Give the assembly a unique name
- ASSEMBLY_TYPE	Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG)
- COVERAGE	50
- PROGRAM	MetaBAT v.2.12.1
- PLATFORM	ILLUMINA
- MOLECULETYPE	genomic DNA
- FASTA	MAG.fasta.gz

4. Now you have everything you need to submit your MAG data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -validate
```

Note: The `-validate` command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

5. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

6. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided an accession for your MAG assembly. Note these down and your submission is complete. Please note, in the case of MAGs an ERZxxx accession is confidential and does not go public. Because MAGs are treated as isolate assemblies, the ENA generates GCA_xxx accessions and sequence accessions for these assemblies as for other genome assemblies. When the assembly completes processing (~48 hours), the submitter receives these accessions by email. Upon submission, only a private ERZxxx accession is assigned.

Return to the interactive Webin interface and view the sample and run tabs to see the objects you submitted today: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>